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A Legal Appraisal of the Protection and Opportunities of Geographical Indication (GI) in Bangladesh

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Abstract

Geographical indication is a sign used on goods that distinguishes a product depending on its place of source and have qualities or a brand image as a result of that source. The research has concentrated on idea of geographical indication, current regulatory mechanisms for geographical indication protection, the ongoing GI issues, a potential GI goods list, and challenges. This article also examines some of the administrative and legal difficulties that nations like Bangladesh confront in assuring its GI protection. The paper strengthens the argument that a Least Developed Country (LDC) like Bangladesh has its business interests in its neighbors substantially affected by the lack of any uniform policy framework to safeguard cross-border GIs. Furthermore, Bangladesh's sui generis GI registration process, which is currently developing, is insufficient to address this issue. To overcome such challenges, some recommendations have been provided. In order to stop other nations from listing and owning their own products, the authors concluded that Bangladesh must act quickly and with significant effort. Any constructive disciplinary action taken by the Bangladesh government in these areas could safeguard their interests.

Keywords: *Geographical Indications (GI), Intellectual Property, TRIPS Agreement, Bangladesh, GI Products*

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Introduction

Geographical indications are words that distinguish an item starting from a specific spot. The Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS) sets out global standards that apply to these terms. Since the selection of the Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights Known as TRIPS Agreement in 1994 which contains a part on unmistakable licensed innovation, this sort of Intellectual property (IP) has pulled in and pulled in growing thought from policymakers and exchange arbitrators, legal advisors just as makers (for the most part of agrarian items). “Countries from South Asia like Bangladesh having improved in conventional and social scholarly properties hold enormous possibilities of financial advancement by legitimate administration of customary and social scholarly properties. World Trade Organization (WTO) Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS) while giving higher status to wines and spirits has let the social events get their own system for guaranteeing geological trademark stock”². The primary function of Bangladesh's licensed innovation system is to grant licenses for the development and enlistment of modern plans, enrollment of exchange and administration imprints, and enrollment of copyrights for writing, imaginative and logical works. “Giving of licenses, enrollment of modern plans and brand names are regulated by the Department of Patents, Designs, and Trademarks (DPDT) under the Ministry of Industries. Before 2013, there was no law in real life for securing our geographically originated or produced goods”³. GI are additional markers of value; to tell shoppers that merchandise comes from a space where a given quality, notoriety, or normal for the products is basically owing to their geographic source⁴. GI has the business interests; to advance the merchandise of specific region and they are qualified for the assurance from encroachments as well as unreasonable rivalries. The TRIPs Agreement was haggled with the goal to give more prominent assurance of IP rights overall which depends on a similar treatment guideline.

Safeguarding of Geographical Indication (International Perspective)

Due to the gradually expanding trans-limit interchange and trade in products with geographical indications, mechanisms for the security GI, the Global access to GI dates to the latter part of the 19th century. Regardless, the national industry assurance of geographical indication by integrating

² Islam, Mohammad Towhidul and Habib, Md., *Introducing Geographical Indications in Bangladesh* (January 12, 2016). *Dhaka University Law Journal* Vol. 24 No. 1 (published in 2016) pp. 51-82., Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2714918>

³ Uddin, M. Kamal, “Report on Innovation and Intellectual Property Policy and Strategy for Bangladesh”, (WIPO) Dhaka.

⁴ Ibid

genuine features was not a surprise. There are a few worldwide products that give geographical indication insurance.⁵

The Paris Convention for the Protection of industrial Property, 1883

GI was acknowledged as a distinct class of intellectual property under the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property in 1883.⁶ According the Paris Convention of 1883, article 10 completely refuses to acknowledge the illegal utilization of “indications of source” on merchandise and gives a few solutions for the concealment of such practices. Article 10 (b) is of the Paris Convention⁷, gives security in opposition to anti - competitive behavior and subsequently on the other side outlines the grounds for assurance against misdirecting source indicators, including appellations of origin.⁸ As per convention “The Paris regime allows the National Treatment Principles to be utilized to preserve the Paris Union's indications of source and indications of origin (AO)”⁹.

Madrid Agreement, 1891

A special agreement spearheaded by WIPO, “the Madrid Agreement for the Prevention of False or Misleading "Indications of Source" on Goods¹⁰ seeks to combat both false indications and misleading sources of source”.¹¹ The real name of the origin of the product can serve as an illusory early indicator of source whilst at the relatively similar time, “regarding the true origin and efficiency of the product, it might be confusing to the buyer. According to Madrid Agreement article 1 (1) suggests that any product carrying a false and deceptive sign by which any of the Madrid Agreement's participating countries or a place¹² designated therein is expressly or implicitly demonstrated to be the same as the nation or place of origin”¹³ Article 11 (3b) requires the Parties to the Agreement to prohibit the use of any indication capable of misleading people in general about the origin of the goods in connection with the sale, display, or offer to be purchased of any products. According to Article 4, national courts must decide whether circumstances are exempt from the Madrid Agreement's rules due to their broad character. The Madrid approach allows for the international registration of the source indication to be safeguarded. The 1891 Convention encompasses both geographic indications and designations of origin due to the expansive

⁵ Cf Islam (n 1)

⁶ Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property, 1967 in Stockholm. According to Article I, Section 2 of the Paris Convention, the mission of industrial property protection.

⁷ (*Trade.ec.europa.eu*, 2022) <https://trade.ec.europa.eu/doclib/docs/2007/june/tradoc_135088.pdf> accessed 28 June 2022.

⁸ 'Paris Convention Of 1883 for The Protection of Industrial Property' (*Abounaja.com*, 2021) <<https://abounaja.com/blogs/paris-convention-of-1883>> accessed 26 June 2022

⁹ Ibid

¹⁰This Agreement is a part of the "Madrid System". See, for details, Giovannucci et al, above note 2, 42-43.

¹¹ cf Islam (n 1)

¹² O'Connor, above note 2, 4.

¹³ Ibid

definition of source indications. Because of this, all parties to this Agreement, including LDCs like Bangladesh, are required to implement border controls on commodities with incorrect or deceptive labels. Since they have the least ability to develop GI to monitor products abroad, least developed nations stand to gain from this agreement¹⁴.

The Lisbon Agreement, 1958 (Registration & Appellations of Origin)

The year of 1958 saw the adoption of the Lisbon Agreement for the Protection of Appellations of Origin and its International Registration. It began operations in 1966, underwent a modification in 1967¹⁵, and underwent its most recent correction in 2002. The Agreement developed the Lisbon System,¹⁶ which is managed by WIPO and is a partner of the Madrid System. Outside of their country origin, it is used to understand and verify Appellations of Origin in countries. By using a single enrollment mechanism for an appellation, and by joining meaningful law, for example, characterizing the substance of the assurance that member states should embrace.¹⁷ In Article 3 of the Agreement, the source designation is given broad assurance, stating that regardless of whether the item's actual origin is given, if the identification is used in a decoded structure, or if the designation is linked by phrases, that surveillance will be assured against such a cession or impersonation or if it's followed by words like kind, type, create, or impersonation, or words to that effect.¹⁸ The Agreement has accommodated a worldwide enrollment framework for "handles of cause" given that they must be first enlisted in the nation of root. "Through a single registration, the Lisbon System for the International Registration of Appellations of Origin provides ways to get insurance for a given name of origin in the parties to the Lisbon Agreement that have signed the agreement. So, if an LDC like Bangladesh turns involved with it, a solitary enlistment would ensure Bangladeshi AOs across the Lisbon umbrella"¹⁹. It would be incredibly beneficial for Bangladeshi AOs to be acquired in international sectors, which might be tough for Bangladesh owing to cost and other essential considerations. Furthermore, there are extra considerations for LDCs, such as Bangladesh, which has a minor voice in amending the Lisbon AO system in order to increase its protective estimation with all GIs other than AO²⁰.

¹⁴ Ahsan Habib, 'Introducing Geographical Indications In Bangladesh' (2013) 24 Dhaka University Law Journal.

¹⁵ Ibid

¹⁶ Lisbon Agreement Article 5.

¹⁷ "Summary of the Lisbon Agreement for the Protection of Appellations of Origin and Their International Registration (1958)" (Summary of the Lisbon agreement for the protection of appellations of origin and their international registration (1958) <https://www.wipo.int/treaties/en/registration/lisbon/summary_lisbon.html> accessed December 28, 2022

¹⁸ Ibid

¹⁹ Cf Islam (n 1)

²⁰ Ibid

The Madrid Agreement, 1989 (Protocol Regarding the Registration of Marks 1891)

Bangladesh chooses to secure its GIs through endorsement signs, index stamps, or assurance signs under brand name structure; it may turn to the Madrid System on the assurance of imprints, which gives total guarantee in the Madrid Union thru a solitary registration. Important imprints, for example, signs or logos, may be safeguarded under the Madrid system on marks.²¹ “This implies that a worldwide enlistment framework for brand names, set up by the Madrid Agreement of 1891 and the Protocol relating to the Madrid Agreement Concerning the International Registration of Marks of 1989, can likewise serve as a means of GI assurance on a worldwide scale”.²²

Bangladesh's Current Legal System for Protecting Geographical Indications

Bangladesh is rich in natural beauty, heritage, and traditional garb. Its animals & plants, folklore, and conventional insight are constantly added to when assembling goods. It has approved “the Geographical Indication of Goods (Registration and Protection) Act 2013”²³ in light of its significant standard set using legitimate and counterfeit resources.²⁴ As the GI Act has been passed and some of our famous products have already been registered by India, Bangladesh has historical, cultural, and geographical roots in Bangladesh's soil for Jamdani and other unique products, If not, Bangladesh would have to pay a surcharge to the Indian government in order using the name Jamdani and other names²⁵. It will assist Bangladeshi manufacturers in differentiating their products from comparable rival items, establishing brand and reputation for local products, and obtaining higher pricing for the products. This will promote sales/exports by safeguarding the local product's reputation²⁶. Bangladesh has lost its rights to some traditional products due to the lack of GI law in the country on the other hand; India has begun registering what is known as a geographical indication (GI) for its products. Therefore, under the Geographical Indications (Registration and Protection) Act of 1999, India has Jamdani Sally, Andhra Pradesh (Uppada), Nakshi Katha in West Bengal, and Fazli Mango in the Malda district of West Bengal (Uppada).

²¹ 'Summary Of the Madrid Agreement Concerning The International Registration Of Marks (1891) And The Protocol Relating To That Agreement (1989)' (Wipo.int, 2021) <https://www.wipo.int/treaties/en/registration/madrid/summary_madrid_marks.html> accessed 13 May 2021.

²² cf Islam (n 1)

²³ Ibid

²⁴ Geographical Indication of Goods (Registration and Protection) Act 2013.

²⁵ Hyder, Md. Nayem Alimul (2016) Geographical Indications Protection In Bangladesh: An Overview. Int. J. Bus. Soc. Sci. Res. 4(2): 95-102. Retrieve from <http://www.ijbssr.com/currentissueview/14013133>.

²⁶ Ibid

Registered as the origin. Jamdani is a unique Bangladeshi hand-woven product with a brilliant history and unique creativity, and Bangladeshi weavers have been making this fine fabric for thousands of years²⁷.

Introducing GI Act in Bangladesh

Bangladesh Government has at last established the much-anticipated Geographical Indication (GI) Act on November 10, 2013. We would now be able to enlist our merchandise and items meriting the GI labels. Bangladesh has a scope of merchandise and items that have the attributes of GI and would effortlessly meet all requirements to the GI alliance. Dhakai Jamdani, Nakshi Kantha, Fazlee-Aam (Mango) from Rajshahi, Hilsha Fish from Chandpur, Rosh Malai from Comilla, Doi (Curd) from Bogra are the most prominent ones among others. It could be recapped that GIs are a sort of licensed innovation that are related with culture, geology, legacy and conventional acts of individuals of a given country. GIs are created in a specific topographical area, which has novel geo-climatic qualities, and this makes them exceptional.²⁸ They associate with the merchandise or results of a domain, or district or region in that country, and set up a connection between the territory and the quality, notoriety or attributes of such merchandise and item. Already, the Draft GI Act, 2012 got the endorsement of the Cabinet Division however was not set at the Parliament as a Bill. All things being equal, “the Draft Act was returned to the Ministry of Industries where it went through a gashing a medical procedure by the Department of Patents, Designs and Trademarks (DPDT) oddly enough”²⁹. DPDT sliced down right around 38 areas from the Draft GI Act, 2012 and planned the 2013 Act dependent on the simple pardon that the segments, that didn't make it to the GI enactment, will ultimately be put in the GI Rules which is normally breathed easy.³⁰

GI Registration System in Bangladesh

Before the law came into force, there was no GI registration process. Currently, the 2013 Geographical Indications of Goods (Registration and Protection) Act and Section 9 provide for how to apply for geographical indications of goods. In accordance with this section, associations, agencies, government agencies, or authorities that represent the interests of those who are configured or registered under applicable law and who create geographical indications of goods shall, in the prescribed form and method, geography of goods³¹. Payment of the prescribed fee for registering indications. If such an individual or group of individuals claims to be a producer, distributor, manufacturer, or processor of a GI

²⁷ Ibid

²⁸ Abu Yusuf, Mohammad and Burhan, Seikh Ruksana, Geographic Indication: The role of the private sector (2013) from The Daily Financial Express (Tuesday, November 12, 2013)

²⁹ cf Hyder (n 24)

³⁰ cf Abu Yusuf (n 27)

³¹ Geographical Indications of Goods (Registration and Protection) Act 2013, s.9

product, they may apply for registration as an authorized user of that GI product under Section 10 increase.³² To complete registration, the Registrar shall publish the application by notification in the prescribed manner if the application is deemed to meet all the requirements of Section 12 of this Code³³. If the registrar believes that the application was made incorrectly or under a different name and title and if they think it doesn't require to register a geographical indication under the circumstances.³⁴ Anyone can refuse to process registration request. Reasonable opportunity agreed to be heard by the applicant in accordance with Section 11. In short, it turns out that the procedure for registering geographical indications in this law is too simple. Without proper steps, no one can register a geographical indication of an item³⁵.

Bangladesh's need for GI protection

Article 24.9 of the TRIPS Agreement completely gives that: " This Agreement will not be bound to secure topographical signs that are not or cease to be secured in their nation of origin or that have been abandoned in that nation"³⁶. So, to conjure an infringement of the WTO TRIPS Agreement, a part concerned should need to initially secure its GI in a structure or another. Then again, any one might be a free rider of a GI on the off chance that it isn't legitimately ensured in its nation of beginning or it has gotten nonexclusive or in any case "has stopped to be secured". For instance, "without a law ensuring the GI in Basmati rice, India would be unable to cope up also with Dispute Settlement or just any WTO Member. One could argue that GI would be protected often without an insurance instrument due to uncalled for rivalry law or the misdeed of passing off"³⁷. Yet, as a general rule passing off activity is entirely capricious and convoluted to demonstrate. An enlisted GI provides the unique feature and customer quality affirmation elements. Great defenders of GI enrollment could claim that it exerts positive effects because it gives small, family-run businesses in rural areas the power to fight against modern consolidation.³⁸ Additionally, the family of traditional practices and native ways of life are currently being impacted by the steadily expanding skyline of globalization.³⁹ Assurance of customary GIs through enlistment is an unavoidable system to forestall bio-robbery and comparable unmerited practices. One may contend that customary geological characteristic names could be ensured under the brand name system. Yet, there are in any event two significant contrasts among trademarks and GI.

³² Geographical Indications of Goods (Registration and Protection) Act 2013, s.10

³³ Geographical Indications of Goods (Registration and Protection) Act 2013, s.12

³⁴ Shipta Barua, 'An Analytical Overview on The Geographical Indication Act | Legal Home' (*Legal Home*, 2021) <<https://legalhome.org/geographical-indication/>> accessed 27 June 2022.

³⁵ Ibid

³⁶ Islam, Mohammad Towhidul and Habib, Md., *Introducing Geographical Indications in Bangladesh* (January 12, 2016). *Dhaka University Law Journal* Vol. 24 No. 1 (published in 2016) pp. 66 .

³⁷ Ibid

³⁸ Ibid

³⁹ cf Abu Yusuf, (n 25)

Without a strong enough legal defense, rivals may complementarily elevate an epithet's standing. Additionally helpful in obtaining a better price search is GI status. In a large number of precise studies, it has been found that a significant portion of consumers are willing to pay more for GI products, but primarily with regard to developed countries. As a non-industrial nation with a solid agrarian area, masterfulness and conventional information, GI law can be a critical public arrangement device for financial turn of events and the business of ranchers and gifted laborer in the field.

The prominent GI goods of Bangladesh

In Bangladesh, GI has immense potential. Dhaka Jamdani, Nakshi Katha, Rajshahi Silk, Sweets, Fazli Mango, Jamdani, Khadi, etc., but because Bangladesh hasn't had a GI law for a while, we haven't been able to boost our financial advantage from this product. As in Bangladesh, this has prevented many people involved in the production of these goods from making economic and social progress.

The Creativity of Bangladeshi Women's Community: Nakshi Kantha

Nakshi kantha, in another name "wrapped quilt", is a type of folk art from Bangladesh and India. For a long time, the craftsmanship has been drilled in rural Bengal. The fundamental material utilized is string and old fabric. Kanthas are made all through Bangladesh, yet the more prominent Mymensingh, Rajshahi, Faridpur and Jessore zones are generally renowned for this craft. The brilliant examples and plans that are weaved brought about the name Nakshi Kantha⁴⁰, which was gotten from the Bengali word Naksha, which alludes to imaginative examples. The early kanthas had a white foundation complemented with red, blue, and dark weaving; later yellow, green, pink and different tones were likewise included. The running line called "kantha line" is the fundamental join utilized for this reason. Generally, Kantha was created for the utilization of the family. Today, after the recovery of the Nakshi Kantha, they are delivered financially. Nakshi Kantha (weaved quilt), said to be native to Bangladesh, is produced using old cotton garments, overwhelmingly disposed of sari, dhoti and lungi.⁴¹

Jamdani

Jamdani is a fine fabric of "muslin" group. A broadly and universally celebrated texture, jamdani is described by geometric or flower plans. Jamdani sarees have colorful direct or flower themes everywhere on the body and have a dazzlingly planned expand pallu.⁴² Bedouin, Chinese and Italian merchants had additionally given nitty gritty record of this texture coming based on what is currently Bangladesh. An

⁴⁰ Ahmed P, The Aesthetics and Vocabulary of Nakshi Kantha (Bangladesh National Museum Collection) <<https://www.exoticindiaart.com/book/details/aesthetics-and-vocabulary-of-nakshi-kantha-bangladesh-national-museum-collection-nak673>> accessed December 28, 2022

⁴¹ Ibid

⁴² Zinat Mahrukh Banu and Masood Reza, Jamdani, <http://www.banglapedia.org/HT/J_0056.htm> 20 Dec 2014.

English explorer, Ralph Finch, likewise praises about muslin and jamdani made in Sonargaon, close to Dhaka.⁴³ The texture, nonetheless, achieved its zenith during the rule of Akbar, the incomparable Mughal Emperor. It had by then gotten such a sought-after thing that the British East India Company who came in later needed to post a high authority in Dhaka to purchase mulmul khas. He was known as the "Daroga-Mulmul." UNESCO has as of late announced the customary craft of Jamdani weaving in Dhaka as a theoretical legacy of mankind⁴⁴.

The King of Fruits: Fazli Mango

Mangoes of the Fazli kind are brought from the eastern region of South Asia (West Bengal and Bihar in India and Bangladesh). This fruit ripens later and became available after other varieties have been much prized in the area. The primary producer of this mango is the Bangladeshi region of Rajshahi. Fazli is a geographical indication that India has applied for; however, Bangladeshi Fazli Mango has already been certified as a product with a Geographical Indication (GI).⁴⁵

Medicinal plants of Bangladesh

In customary and elective restorative practices like Unani and Ayurvedic frameworks, conventional therapeutic plants have been broadly utilized roots in Bangladesh.⁴⁶ Apparently, the beneficiaries of these frameworks of medication give off an impression of being the provincial individuals, yet for all intents and purposes a decent extent of the metropolitan populace actually keeps on utilizing these conventional prescriptions, albeit coordinated present-day medical services offices are accessible to them. Medicinal arrangements, practically all of which circular segment multi-componential, utilized in these two frameworks bend perpetually produced using plant materials, in some cases with the expansion of some creature items and furthermore some common or manufactured natural and inorganic synthetic substances, major dynamic compound right now or once got from (or designed after) intensifies got from organic variety.⁴⁷

⁴³ Ibid

⁴⁴ 'UNESCO - Traditional Art of Jamdani Weaving' (*Ich.unesco.org*, 2015) <<https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/traditional-art-of-jamdani-weaving-00879>> accessed 28 June 2022.

⁴⁵ "Fazli Mango Gets Gi Recognition - Countryside" (*The Daily Observer* October 22, 2021) <<https://observerbd.com/news.php?id=336402>> accessed December 23, 2022

⁴⁶ 3 Mohammad Abdur Rahman, 'Conservation of Medicinal Plants in Bangladesh' (Paper prepared for presentation at the Annual Bangladesh Botanical Conference, 2006).

⁴⁷ *ibid*

Certified GI Products in Bangladesh

As of 17 May 2022, Bangladesh has total 10 (Ten)⁴⁸ GI certified products, Last addition is 'Bagda Prawn'. The department of fisheries applied for GI certification in May 2019 to promote Bagda Prawn in the international market. The Patent, Design and Trademark Office published the official bulletin on October 6, last year, and published it in two journals. If no one disagrees within two months of being published in a trade magazine, there is nothing to prevent the product from obtaining a GI certificate in accordance with regulations⁴⁹. In 2016, Jamdani was designated as Bangladesh's first geographical indication product. Hilsha acquired the geographical indication in 2017, and Kirsia Patti Mango acquired the geographical indication in 2019. On September 24, 2017, the "Bangladesh Silk Development Commission, Rajshahi, applied for the geographical rights of Rajshahi Silk among the six new GI products. Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI) applied for a GI certificate for Karijira Rice on February 7, 2017. BRRI has also applied for a GI certificate for Kataribhog from Dinajpur"⁵⁰. The Deputy Chief Cabinet Secretary of Netrokona applied to receive a GI from Sadamati of Bijoypur on February 6, 2017. An application to obtain a Dhakai Muslin GI certificate from the Handloom Board, Bangladesh was received on January 2, 2018.⁵¹

The list of 11 (Eleven) GI products are given below:

1. Jamdani
2. Hilsha Fish
3. Khirsapat Mango of Chapainawabganj
4. Muslin of Dhaka
5. Silk of Rajshahi
6. Shatranji of Rangpur
7. Kataribhog Rice of Dinajpur

⁴⁸ The Business Standard, 'Bagda Prawn Receives GI Certificate' (2022) <<https://www.tbsnews.net/economy/bagda-prawn-receives-gi-certificate-421706>> accessed 1 July 2022

⁴⁹ Ibid

⁵⁰ Likhon N, "Six New Items Gain GI Status" (Bangladesh Post April 23, 2021) <<https://bangladeshpost.net/posts/six-new-items-gain-gi-status-58682>> accessed December 28, 2022

⁵¹ Ibid.

8. Kalijira Rice of Dinajpur⁵²
9. Clay-crystalline cellulose composite of Bijoypur in Netrokona
10. Bagda Prawn
11. Fazli Mango

In response to inquiries, “Mr. Abdus Sattar, Registrar of DPDT, stated to Bangladesh Post: "We had hoped to deliver the six new product certifications on 2021 April 26, the day of intellectual property rights, but owing to restrictions, it is not possible”⁵³. Since the certificate must be physically handed, we want to distribute it following the EID at a convenient time. The DPDT also stated that it had applied for GI certification for 29 additional goods. One famous example is the Anabus fish (Kai fish). Some of these may receive final GI recognition.

Essential of GI’s recognition in Marketing Value of Product

Interest in GIs has flourished recently in Bangladesh. The commitment, under the TRIPS Agreement, for Members of the World Trade Organization (WTO) to ensure GIs has, generally, set off this consideration. However, what makes the fascination? The short answer is that they are viewed as valuable tools or mechanisms in advertising systems and public strategies, for which there has been developing revenue in the last a few decades. Topographical signs as separation apparatuses in showcasing systems: from simple source markers to brands Consumers give expanding consideration to the geographical origin of products and care about explicit qualities present in the items they purchase.⁵⁴ Now and again, the "spot of the beginning" recommends to buyers that the product will have a specific quality or trademark that they may esteem. Frequently, customers are set up to pay more for such items. This has supported the advancement of explicit business sectors for items with specific qualities connected to their geographical place of origin.⁵⁵ Brand acknowledgment is a fundamental part of advertising. Geographical indications convey information about the beginning bound characteristics of a product. They along these lines work as product differentiators available by empowering buyers to recognize items with geological Indication attributes and others without those qualities. Topographical signs would thus be able to be a vital component in developing brands for quality-bound-to-origin products. So, it is easily thinkable that the Geographical Indication recognized products are having more value than a random product, due to its

⁵² Asjadul Kibria, 'Getting Products GI-Tagged' The Financial Express (2021) <<https://thefinancialexpress.com.bd/views/getting-products-gi-tagged-1624722272>> accessed 1 July 2022.

⁵³ cf Likhon (n 49)

⁵⁴ World Intellectual Property Organization, *Geographical Indications* (World Intellectual Property Organization 2015).

⁵⁵ Ibid

uniqueness, and historical or popularity of the product keep those products ahead of others.⁵⁶ Additionally, the increased desire to pay of customers may be used to produce a higher value premium with the GI⁵⁷. Like brand names, GIs are the most important resources for the producers since they give rivalry control and have a commitment to keep up this benefit.⁵⁸ The advertising cost of making another brand name is very high for the producers. However, GIs do not require such a high cost since they have a set up and continuous standing.⁵⁹ “They have been now popular for their quality and attributes and there is no requirement for an additional expense for advertising. While the vast majority of GIs are created in country territories, the neighborhood producers enjoy a benefit to utilize these pointers as a showcasing apparatus under lower costs”⁶⁰. GIs subsequently have an immediate commitment for the makers⁶¹. Comparing with the other developed and developing nations, the GI assurance of Bangladesh at the public and worldwide level is very low, which implies that Bangladesh doesn't accumulate every one of the possible advantages from the insurance of GIs. Numerous studies conducted all around the world demonstrate a rise in “pricing, marketing power, employment, and revenue due to GI security”⁶². As a result, Bangladesh should incorporate the problem of GI insurance into its political strategy as a means of generating marketing, money, and jobs, and ultimately as a means of advancing the area.

GI's Product in Rural Development

Various examinations demonstrate that, under fitting conditions, GIs can add to advancement in rural areas. The qualification to utilize a GI by and large lies with producers, and the additional worth created by the GI gathers along these lines to every such producer. Since GI products will in general produce a premium brand value, they add to nearby business creation, which ultimately may help to prevent provincial mass migration. Also, GI items regularly have significant spin-off effects, for instance in the space of the tourism industry and gastronomy. Geological signs may bring value to a region not just as far as occupations and higher pay, yet additionally by advancing the locale overall. In such manner, GIs may

⁵⁶ Ibid

⁵⁷ Dogan B and Gokovali U, “Geographical Indications: The Aspects of Rural Development and Marketing through the Traditional Products” (2012) 62 *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 761

⁵⁸ Bilge Dogan and Ummuhan Gokovali, 'Geographical Indications: The Aspects of Rural Development and Marketing Through The Traditional Products' (2012) 62 *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*.

⁵⁹ Ibid

⁶⁰ cf Dogan (n 53)

⁶¹ Khondkar M, “Geographical Indication (GI): A Way to Promote Our Brands in the Global Market” (2014) 31 *Social Science Review*

⁶² cf Dogan (n 53)

add to the making of a "regional brand." An expression of alert is, the simple actuality of building up a GI for an item doesn't ensure programmed achievement or improvement for the locale.⁶³

For GIs to add to advancement, a few conditions should be available around there and in the manner by which the particular GI plan is planned.⁶⁴ Traditional goods are viewed as sentimental and fascinating local goods as they combine common assets with social strategies to represent the local feature.⁶⁵ As a conventional product bunch, GIs highlight the item's geological name as an appealing technique for drawing consumers' attention into the local identity. This would result in a growth of travel and tourist business activities across rural regions. Hence viable insurance of GIs leads not exclusively to expand the acknowledgment of the creation put yet additionally make some outer advantages, for example, expansion in monetary action of different areas that have in reverse and forward linkages with the GI products. For example, expansion in the tourism industry movement because of perceived GI advantages to the producer as well as sets out pay and work open doors to different areas, for example, in administrations for restaurants, gift stores, and hospitality services for lodging. Increased life standards in rural regions are facilitated by economic activity, settlement, and security of GI business sectors⁶⁶. In this manner GI, insurance contributes the rural manageable economy as well as ensures the social legacy too. GIs establish a connection between the name of the geological area where the product comes from and the product itself. As a result, these characteristics are a useful marketing tool for attracting consumers' attention to the geological areas. The majority of these geographic regions have been rural, and GIs offer essential freedoms to rural developments. Assurance of GIs could assist with supporting monetary exercises and repayment in rural regions and raise the standard of living for the locals.⁶⁷ Regarding salary and business age, the local populace is the biggest beneficiary of these types of items.

Challenges of GI in Bangladesh

The 'Geographic Indication Act, 2013' has been dependent on the DPDT who will open a separate unit named 'Geographical Indication Unit' to do the exercises identified with enrolment and insurance of GIs as implied under the Act. The GI Unit will be led by the DPDT's Registrar. According to the GI law, "any

⁶³ Hoang Truong Giang and Nguyen Hoang Anh, Geographical Indications Sand Sustainable Rural Development in Vietnam (2021)

<<https://www.unescap.org/sites/default/files/Geographical%20Indications%20and%20Sustainable%20Rural%20Development%20in%20Vietnam.pdf>> accessed 9 May 2021.

⁶⁴ Ibid

⁶⁵ Bilge Dogan and Ummuhan Gokovali, 'Geographical Indications: The Aspects Of Rural Development And Marketing Through The Traditional Products' (2012) 62 Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences.

⁶⁶ Ibid

⁶⁷ Ibid

person chosen to address the public interest of the producers of GI products, or any legal organization, affiliation, or government body, may apply to the Registrar for enrolment of GI goods or items⁶⁸. In addition, any person or group involved in providing GI goods may apply to be listed as an authorized consumer of such GI goods or items⁶⁹. Unfortunately, the arrangements that were cut off comprised a few of explicit arrangements that are required again for enrolling measure. Because of how difficult it was to develop the GI Act, this expresses concern. It required thorough missions, requests produced using different pressing factor gatherings and common society, public counsels, and subsequent meet-ups did over a decent number of years. Presently it is fascinating to its obvious, with respect to “how long the concerned Ministry would devour to present the Rules under the geographical Indications Act, 2013”⁷⁰. In Bangladesh, for example, It took six years for the concern authority to submit the Copyright Rules after the Copyright Act was passed in 2000⁷¹. The enrolled approved consumer of GI products, whose residency to use GI products or items has been lowered to a long time from 10 years as it was contemplated in the Proposed GI Act 2012, was not included in DPDT's cutting binge. Actually, the residence requirement for enrolling in GI goods or items has made the stay legitimate until the enrolments are cancelled or deemed invalid. This will permit the GI merchandise or items to try not to go through reestablishments after a specific timeframe - because of DPDT's frightening intelligence. Besides all of these, confusion regarding patent versus GI recognitions and TRIPS agreement with bilateral agreement that happened within particular region is also need to clear to rid out of these challenges.⁷²

Recommendations

- ◆ First and foremost, the Department of Patents, Designs, and Trademarks (DPDT) should make solid and compelling strides as to GI merchandise in Bangladesh.
- ◆ The DPDT GI unit should have a detailed list of GI goods from around the country as an essential information base for nearby products. The GI Act, 2013 may secure the nation's cases to items, for example, jamdani saree, Hilsha fish, nakshi kantha, fazli mango, and some other popular food sources of Bangladesh.

⁶⁸ Rubel, “Challenges and Protection of Bangladesh GI Goods” (OurtimeBDMarch 22, 2020) <<https://www.ourtimebd.com/beta/challenges-and-protection-of-bangladesh-gi-goods>> accessed December 23, 2022

⁶⁹ cf Hyder (n 24)

⁷⁰ Ibid

⁷¹ Ibid

⁷² Barua S, “5 Challenges to Protecting of Geographical Indication” <<https://legalhome.org/protecting-geographical-indication/#:~:text=There%20are%20a%20number%20of,along%20with%20the%20TRIPS%20Agreement>> accessed December 23, 2022

- ◆ In terms of GI security, Bangladesh should align its policies and procedures with international treaties, such as the Madrid Agreement, Lisbon Agreement, Paris Convention and TRIPS Agreement etc.
- ◆ In order to prevent the mediation of the GI enlistment center wing in DPDT The recorder office must limit the scope of its vast jurisdiction.
- ◆ Registration process seems to be cumbersome and time consuming. Therefore, the registration process should be transparent, convenient and expeditious to limit unnecessary procedures.
- ◆ Regarding profitable systems, the period of detention and penalties for violating the GI Act must be adequate.
- ◆ The public authority should have to organize customary preparing on licensed innovation rights concerns among the law upholding organizations and legal authorities that can procure sensible information and encounters on the concerned issue.
- ◆ Create a better environment to protect GI goods; A Sui Generis Act must be enacted to protect cultural knowledge.
- ◆ The GI reign made no mention of the GI inspection structure required to ensure and sustain the stated quality of GI products.
- ◆ By utilizing media and other strategies, the government authorities might organize a public awareness campaign about the relevance of GIs in Bangladesh.
- ◆ At last, government and every one of the partners identifying with Geographical indication products must make great efforts to protect the rights of GIs in Bangladesh.

Concluding Remarks

In spite of the fact that they are probably the most established type of IP, GIs have as of late become the subject of summed up interest. In numerous nations, the need to consent to commitments under the TRIPS Agreement set off this emphasis on GIs. Nations soon realized the potential value of this form of intellectual property. The placement of GIs in a region suggests that they could be effective tools for developing privately based events. Their nearby linkage with custom proposes that they can emphatically affect the protection of TCEs and TK. With the growing recognition of Geographical Indication (GI) multifunctional nature, the challenge will be to develop and carry out a comprehensive GI strategy which

could be the cause of an economic turn of events. This analysis outlines some of the methodological considerations associated with improving GI planning, as well as some of the factors and circumstances that contribute to its success. It then concentrates upon one of several prerequisites, specifically the protection of GIs as an IP right. Plainly actual security of GIs should not be taken for granted, and it is not a necessary component of a successful GI. Nonetheless, it is also noteworthy that even failure to adequately secure GIs as IP can toss over the edge even the most adjusted, improvement situated GI plan.

Protecting GI goods is of great benefits both inventors and users, whether in developed, developing, or least developed countries. Bangladesh has compiled a list of goods, both food- and non-food-related, which can be deemed GI. After registration, even greater steps need to be made to prevent neighboring countries from duplicating Bangladesh's GI, as happened in Jamdani sari, Fazli Mango, Uppada Jamdani Saree, and Nakshi Katha⁷³. India has many goods on the GI list. We don't know if more Bangladeshi GIs would desire to follow in India's footsteps in the future⁷⁴. However, this should serve as a wake-up call in Bangladesh. English Philosopher and Attorney General Francis Bacon once said "*Silence is the virtue of fools*" in the same manner Samuel Taylor Coleridge an English poet wrote "*Silence does not necessarily denote wisdom*". In this circumstance, we must remember these phrases.

⁷³ Samiun Bhuiyan, 'Measures of The Protection of Geographical Indications in Bangladesh' (Academia.edu, 2016) <https://www.academia.edu/50248100/Measures_of_the_protection_of_Geographical_Indications_in_Bangladesh> accessed 28 June 2022.

⁷⁴ Ibid